

Living Lab in the Poultry Sector in Vietnam

Living Lab Coordinator(s)
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Poultry sector

Chicken

The Vietnamese poultry Living Lab consisted of 15 participants from 7 types of organizations (veterinary services at provincial, district and communal level; farmer; veterinarian; drug seller; drug company; chicken retailer; university professor) to come up with ways to reduce antimicrobial use (AMU) at local level. Half of the group had participated in individual interviews and more participants were invited to represent the whole sector. The Living Lab carried through different strategies, and 2 plan of actions for an 'Action Lab' were created. The Living Lab consisted of 3 meetings at local level during 3 weeks in April 2022. The Action Lab might be implemented in the near future.

The strategy tested in the Living Lab

The first strategy aimed to increase awareness of farmers and consumers on the need to reduce AMU, good biosecurity practices, and organic production by broadcasting videos on national TV twice a week in the evening. The content of the videos will be based on a preliminary survey to assess the need of the targeted audience, and produced by TV channels in line with the ministry of agriculture's recommendations. Livestream will be conducted in model farms that have implemented good biosecurity and/or organic production.

The second strategy aimed to organize training for drug sellers on AMU, AMR, biosecurity, and organic production. Training will be provided by drug companies, university professors, and agricultural service centers. Training will also be broadcasted online and flyers will be produced.

The roadmap to implementation

To co-develop strategies to reduce AMU in poultry production in Vietnam, the ImpresS ex ante methodology was used. This methodology started with the definition of a shared vision of the future to improve biosecurity and develop organic production at farm level. Participants identified several barriers to reach this common vision as the lack of outputs for organic products, lack of sciences and technologies, inadequate training and high proportion of small-scale farms.

Participants decided to focus on improving trainings and awareness on biosecurity and organic production for farmers, drug sellers, and consumers. Training courses should be better adapted to the constraints of the field by assessing the need of farmers.

The impact created by the Living Lab

AMU: The Living Lab created a discussion group on AMU and AMR topics between different categories of stakeholders including public and private sectors. Solutions to reduce AMU might be disseminated to other actors through the participant's network. Improving biosecurity will contribute to reducing disease incidence and thus AMU and organic production standards will tend to reduce AMU.

Animal health: Training courses will contribute to the reduction of animal disease burden at farm levels through better biosecurity practices and the usage of alternative feed additives.

Costs and savings: The Living Lab will contribute to increasing the livelihood of farmers by reducing animal disease costs and antibiotic costs. The development of organic production could also lead to a better valorization of the products through specialized selling channels.

Challenges

- Consumers, small scale farmers and drug company (that only sell AB) were not included
- Time constraints to implement the ImpresS ex ante method and to implement the Action Lab
- Dissemination of the results to the national level

Successes

- All participants were able to give their opinion
- High level of attendance: 13 on 15 participants attended to the 3 workshops
- Exchange of knowledge and experience between different types of organizations
- Ownership of the methodology and results by the research team

Reducing AMU in Vietnam requires multiple solutions including the improvement of training and awareness programmes, developing other forms of socio-economic organization such as cooperatives, and new quality standards. Strategies developed must now be shared with policy-makers and be implemented.

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